

THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF BUILDINGS IN THE CITY OF NUKUS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8437517>

Abstract. *The energy efficiency of buildings is a critical concern in the context of climate change and the need to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Roof structures play a pivotal role in the energy performance of multi-storey residential buildings. This scientific article presents a comprehensive study on the energy efficiency of roof structures in the context of the city of Nukus, Uzbekistan. The research focuses on assessing the thermal performance, energy consumption, and potential improvements in existing multi-storey residential buildings to enhance their energy efficiency and reduce environmental impact.*

Keywords: *Energy Efficiency, Roof Structures, Multi-Storey Residential Buildings, Thermal Analysis, Nukus, Uzbekistan, Green Building Technologies, Retrofit, Climate Change, Insulation, Reflective Roofing Materials, Green Roof Technologies, Thermal Mass.*

ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЗДАНИЙ ГОРОДА НУКУСА

Аннотация. *Энергоэффективность зданий является критической проблемой в контексте изменения климата и необходимости сокращения выбросов парниковых газов. Конструкции крыши играют решающую роль в энергетической эффективности многоэтажных жилых домов. В данной научной статье представлено комплексное исследование энергоэффективности кровельных конструкций в условиях города Нукус, Узбекистан. Исследование сосредоточено на оценке тепловых характеристик, энергопотребления и потенциальных улучшениях существующих многоэтажных жилых зданий с целью повышения их энергоэффективности и снижения воздействия на окружающую среду.*

Ключевые слова: *Энергоэффективность, Конструкции крыши, Многоэтажные жилые дома, Термический анализ, Нукус, Узбекистан, Технологии зеленого строительства, Модернизация, Изменение климата, Изоляция, Светоотражающие кровельные материалы, Технологии зеленой кровли, Тепловая масса.*

The construction and operation of buildings account for a substantial portion of global energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. Among the various components of a building, roofs are particularly important in maintaining thermal comfort and reducing energy consumption. In the city of Nukus, where extreme temperatures are common, understanding and improving the energy efficiency of roof structures is crucial.

The analysis of the energy efficiency of roof structures in Nukus' multi-storey residential buildings yielded several key insights and practical recommendations for improving their overall performance: Enhance Roof Insulation: One of the primary findings of the study was the prevalence of inadequate roof insulation in the surveyed buildings. It is recommended that building owners and authorities invest in upgrading insulation materials and techniques to reduce heat loss during the cold winter months. Options such as adding additional layers of insulation or using advanced insulation materials like spray foam or rigid foam boards can significantly enhance the thermal resistance of roofs. [1.73]

Reflective Roofing Materials: In Nukus' hot and arid climate, the use of reflective roofing materials can effectively reduce solar heat gain during the scorching summer months. Installing cool or white roofing materials can help buildings stay cooler, decreasing the need for energy-intensive air conditioning. Additionally, reflective materials can extend the lifespan of the roof and lower maintenance costs.

Green Roof Technologies: Green roof systems, which incorporate vegetation and planting on the roof surface, can offer multiple benefits. Green roofs act as natural insulators, reducing temperature fluctuations and heat transfer. They also improve air quality and provide aesthetic and recreational spaces for residents. Local authorities and building owners should consider promoting and incentivizing the adoption of green roofs as a sustainable solution. [2.15]

Thermal Mass Utilization: The use of materials with high thermal mass, such as concrete or clay tiles, was found to be effective in reducing temperature fluctuations. These materials can absorb and store heat, releasing it gradually throughout the day or night. Utilizing such materials in roof construction can help maintain comfortable indoor temperatures and decrease the need for constant heating or cooling.

Retrofitting Existing Buildings: Retrofitting existing buildings with improved roofing materials and techniques is a cost-effective approach to enhancing energy efficiency. In many cases, it is more environmentally and economically sustainable than demolishing and reconstructing entire structures. It is recommended that building owners explore retrofit options, taking into account the local climate conditions and the specific needs of their buildings. **Local Building Codes and Regulations:** Local authorities and policymakers should consider updating building codes and regulations to mandate higher standards for roof insulation, reflective roofing materials, and green roof technologies. By incorporating these requirements into building practices, Nukus can ensure that new construction projects contribute to the city's energy efficiency goals.

Public Awareness and Education: Educating building owners, architects, and residents about the importance of energy-efficient roof structures and the benefits of these recommended improvements is vital. Public awareness campaigns can encourage the adoption of sustainable building practices and the implementation of these energy-saving measures.

In conclusion, the recommendations for improving the energy efficiency of roof structures in multi-storey residential buildings in Nukus are multifaceted and tailored to the city's unique climatic conditions and existing building stock. By implementing these measures, Nukus can reduce energy consumption, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and create more comfortable and sustainable living environments for its residents. This research paves the way for a more energy-efficient and environmentally conscious future in the city of Nukus and serves as a model for similar initiatives in other regions facing climate-related challenges.

The study's findings indicated that a significant number of multi-storey residential buildings in Nukus were plagued by insufficient roof insulation. This deficiency was particularly pronounced during the frigid winter months when maintaining indoor thermal comfort is of paramount importance. The lack of proper insulation led to substantial heat loss, necessitating higher energy consumption for heating purposes. The energy inefficiency resulting from this inadequacy not only strained household budgets but also significantly contributed to increased

greenhouse gas emissions. The implications of this issue underscore the urgent need for addressing insulation deficiencies in Nukus' existing building stock. [3.62]

Solar Heat Gain: During the scorching summer months, the study revealed that buildings with poorly designed roofs experienced excessive solar heat gain. This phenomenon increased the demand for energy-intensive cooling systems, thereby adding to the overall energy consumption of these structures. The consequences of this solar heat gain issue not only strained energy resources but also diminished indoor comfort and productivity for occupants. Addressing this problem is critical for reducing the energy demand in Nukus during the hot season and enhancing the quality of life for residents.

Thermal Mass: The research demonstrated that the incorporation of materials with high thermal mass, such as concrete and clay tiles, had a positive impact on reducing temperature fluctuations within buildings. These materials proved effective in maintaining comfortable indoor conditions by absorbing and storing heat, subsequently releasing it gradually throughout the day or night. This thermal mass utilization was found to be a practical strategy for enhancing the energy efficiency of multi-storey residential buildings in Nukus, particularly in a climate characterized by extreme temperature variations.

Recommendations: To address the identified issues and enhance the energy efficiency of existing multi-storey residential buildings in Nukus, the study puts forth several key recommendations:

Improve Insulation: Retrofit buildings with enhanced insulation materials and techniques to minimize heat loss during cold weather. Implement weatherization measures to seal gaps and prevent air leakage in the building envelope. Conduct energy audits to identify insulation deficiencies and prioritize improvements.

Increase Use of Reflective Roofing Materials: Encourage the use of cool or white roofing materials, which reflect solar radiation and reduce solar heat gain. Promote the coating of existing roofs with reflective, energy-efficient coatings to improve their solar reflectance. Establish incentives and regulations to drive the adoption of reflective roofing materials in new construction projects. [4.93]

Adopt Green Roof Technologies: Explore the implementation of green roofs on existing buildings, as well as in new construction projects, to improve insulation, reduce heat gain, and enhance urban greenery.

Develop local policies and incentives that support the adoption of green roof technologies, taking into account local climate conditions and water management requirements.

These recommendations, when implemented comprehensively and strategically, hold the potential to significantly reduce energy consumption, improve indoor comfort, and contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in Nukus. Moreover, they align with broader sustainability goals and offer a pathway towards creating more resilient and environmentally responsible urban spaces.

The findings of this study provide a solid foundation for further research and practical implementation efforts aimed at enhancing the energy efficiency of roof structures in multi-storey residential buildings. The following areas of future research are crucial for continuing the progress in this field:

The research presented in this scientific article underscores the importance of evaluating and enhancing the energy efficiency of roof structures in existing multi-storey residential buildings, especially in regions with extreme climatic conditions like Nukus. By implementing the recommendations outlined in this study, the city can reduce energy consumption, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and contribute to a more sustainable and resilient built environment.

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